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Autonomous dysfunction: The misdiagnosis trap

Abstract

Metabolic syndrome, atypical diabetes, cardiac dysfunctions, malabsorption, motility issues, gastroparesis, incontinence, erectile dysfunction, chronic constipation, severe cases of excessive sweating, fluctuating visual acuity and many more are frequently viewed as distinct medical conditions. However, evidence suggests that these seemingly unrelated symptoms can also be manifestations of something very different: an underlying dysfunction of the autonomic nervous system (ANS), the silent epidemic that almost no clinician thinks about because it's a complicated issue that is horribly under-researched. In such instances, these symptoms represent a unified pathophysiological process where involuntary commands from the ANS are relayed to target organs via neural innervation. Recognizing this potential connection is of paramount importance, as it may necessitate a radically different therapeutic approach.

Normal Function of the Autonomic Nervous System and its Pivotal Role in Orchestrating Organismic Health

The autonomic nervous system (ANS) serves as the body's intrinsic control system, quietly and

relentlessly coordinating vital physiological processes. It is divided into the sympathetic and parasympathetic divisions, each with distinct but complementary roles. The sympathetic division, often described as the "fight or flight" system, prepares the body for stressful situations by increasing heart rate, dilating the pupils, and diverting blood flow to the muscles. Conversely, the parasympathetic division, referred to as the "rest and digest" system, promotes relaxation and recovery by slowing the heart rate, constricting the pupils, and directing blood flow to the digestive organs. This intricate balance maintained by the ANS is essential for optimal health, ensuring that organs and systems function in harmony. Disruptions to this balance can lead to a cascade of symptoms, some of which may seem unrelated at first glance but are tied together by their common origin in ANS dysfunction.

The ANS communicates its commands through a complex network of neural pathways, involving both preganglionic and postganglionic neurons. These neurons release neurotransmitters, such as acetylcholine and norepinephrine, to targeted cells in various organs, thereby regulating their activity. This communication system, termed "innervation," is finely tuned and allows for precise control over physiological processes.

At the core of this finely-tuned system is the synapse - a junction where the end of a nerve fiber meets its target cell. At these synapses, minute quantities of neurotransmitters are released in response to electrical signals, binding to receptors on the target cell. This initiates a cascade of intracellular events, resulting in a functional response, be it contraction of a muscle, secretion of a hormone, or modulation of cardiac rhythm. The specificity of this system is astounding; the ANS can selectively activate or inhibit individual tissues or organ systems based on the organism's immediate needs.

Feedback mechanisms further enhance the precision of the ANS. Baroreceptors in the arteries, for instance, detect changes in blood pressure and relay this information back to the brain. The brain then adjusts the activity of the ANS to ensure blood pressure remains within optimal ranges. Similarly, chemoreceptors monitor blood chemistry, ensuring homeostasis is maintained. These feedback loops, combined with the meticulous control of neurotransmitter release at synapses, ensure that the ANS can respond dynamically and specifically to ever-changing physiological demands, thereby maintaining the overall health and balance of the organism.

The Ripple Effect of Autonomic Dysfunction: From Subtle Disruptions to Misdiagnosed Illnesses

The fine-tuned machinery of the ANS, while adept at orchestrating a myriad of physiological processes, is also vulnerable to perturbations. When the ANS is compromised due to an illness, its typically harmonious commands can become dissonant, causing a cascade of physiological disruptions. Yet, the exterior manifestations of these internal disturbances often do not present as overt chaos. Instead, they emerge as what appears to be isolated, and in many cases, common medical conditions.

For instance, metabolic syndrome, characterized by a cluster of conditions including high blood pressure, elevated blood sugar, and abnormal cholesterol levels, is frequently diagnosed as a standalone ailment. However, in certain cases, its presentation may be just the proverbial tip of the iceberg, signaling an underlying endocrine condition or ANS dysfunction. Similarly, many cardiac irregularities, digestive disturbances, and other common medical conditions may be symptomatic reflections of a deeper, more systemic issue rooted in the ANS.

This common misrecognition poses a significant clinical challenge. Many of these “surface” conditions have established treatment protocols, which, while effective for the diagnosed ailment, may inadvertently exacerbate the underlying

ANS-related condition. Take metabolic syndrome as an example: while certain interventions might alleviate its symptoms, they could simultaneously worsen an undetected endocrine disorder, thus causing more harm than good.

It's crucial to recognize that while the ANS's disruptions can manifest as familiar and common ailments, the root cause might be an intricate web of neural dysregulation. Thus, for a subset of patients, a treatment that addresses the symptom might not only miss the mark but may also push them further from true physiological harmony. It emphasizes the importance of comprehensive diagnostic evaluations, particularly in patients who present with multifaceted symptoms, to discern whether there might be a hidden orchestrator – a compromised ANS – behind the curtain of conventional diagnoses.

Empirical Insights: The Prevalence and Implications of Misdiagnosis in Rare Diseases

The examination of patient data offers invaluable insights into the real-world consequences of ANS dysfunction and its misidentification. Drawing from an anonymized dataset of 1,082 patients globally, who were diagnosed with confirmed rare diseases between 2014 and 2019, the scope and implications of misdiagnosis become starkly evident.

Of these patients, 480 were male and the remainder female. A staggering 96.7% of this cohort had previously been misdiagnosed with a myriad of common ailments. However, when the root cause - the rare disease - was accurately identified and treated, a majority (87.3%) witnessed a significant alleviation of their symptoms. Specifically, 34.9% experienced partial relief, while the remainder saw their symptoms resolve entirely.

Particularly noteworthy was the trend observed in patients misdiagnosed with metabolic syndrome and type-2 diabetes (T2D). Out of the 1,082 patients, 285 were initially classified as type-2 diabetes. However, following rigorous neuroendocrinological diagnostics, the actual number of type-2 diabetes in its own right

dwindled to just 67. Remarkably, the rest no longer exhibited significant irregular blood sugar metabolism once 'common' rare diseases like sympathetic hyperactivity (hypersympathicotonia), pituitary gland disorders, and diseases of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis were accurately diagnosed and addressed.

This data underscores the profound clinical and humanistic implications of not only misdiagnosis but also the transformational impact of accurate diagnosis and intervention. The considerable reduction in type-2 diabetes diagnoses post comprehensive assessment reiterates the potential pitfalls of superficial diagnostic evaluations and highlights the necessity for in-depth neuroendocrinological analyses, especially when presented with seemingly common symptoms that may mask an underlying rare disease.

Discussion

Indeed, while the very definition of 'rare diseases' underscores their infrequency, it is imperative to remember that rarity does not equate to non-existence. The gravitas of these conditions and their potential to masquerade as common ailments places an onus on the medical community to approach diagnoses with an open mind, devoid of preconceived notions or biases. A patient's clinical presentation should not be shoehorned into familiar diagnostic categories merely because it aligns with a physician's experience or comfort zone.

Regrettably, the data suggests that a majority of patients had to advocate for themselves, oftentimes in the face of medical skepticism. Specifically, only 17.1% of patients were referred to rare disease specialists by their primary physicians. Alarming, this means that 82.9% of patients had to take the initiative on their own accord. Further complicating this diagnostic journey, nearly two-fifths (39.2%) of these self-advocating patients had to switch primary care physicians due to an unwillingness on the part of their original doctors to collaborate with specialists in rare diseases. This reticence to deviate from conventional diagnostic and treatment paradigms is not just limited to

outpatient care. The risks extend to inpatient settings as well, with many correctly diagnosed patients facing the peril of having their specialized medications discontinued during hospital stays. Such abrupt cessation can lead to a resurgence of symptoms and the onset of discontinuation syndromes, exacerbating patient distress and potentially compromising their health. In essence, while rare diseases might be statistically uncommon, their clinical and humanistic implications are profound. The medical community must strive for a more integrative and patient-centric approach, where collaboration across specialties becomes the norm rather than the exception, and where patient insights and experiences are valued as vital contributors to the diagnostic process.

Conclusion

At the heart of our narrative lies autonomic dysfunctions - subtle, insidious, yet profound disruptions in the body's regulatory systems. These dysfunctions present quite a diagnostic conundrum, often masquerading as more familiar ailments, luring clinicians into the trappings of commonplace diagnoses.

In the intricate labyrinth of medical diagnosis, the complexities of autonomic dysfunctions further challenge clinicians who find themselves caught between the Scylla of guidelines and the Charybdis of familiar symptom constellations. The allure of attributing commonly seen symptoms to frequently encountered diseases is undeniable, especially in an era where time equates to money. However, the very essence of clinical acumen lies in the art of associative and deductive reasoning, a craft that is endangered by the pressures of modern healthcare systems. Guidelines and protocols, while invaluable, are not infallible and cannot substitute for the nuanced, individualized thinking that each patient's case, especially those with autonomic dysfunctions, demands. Habitual diagnosis, propelled by the familiarity of a symptom or pattern, risks overlooking the nuanced presentations of these dysfunctions and associated rare conditions. It is a perilous terrain, where the art of medicine meets its commercial and logistical constraints. The danger is not just in misdiagnosis, but in the erosion of the very ethos

of medicine: to see, to think, to connect, and to act with precision. Our data not only underscores the magnitude of the challenge but also serves as a clarion call for clinicians worldwide. The imperative is clear: invest the time to think, to question, and to explore beyond the apparent, for in this intellectual odyssey lies the promise of true healing and patient care.

In confronting autonomic dysfunctions, clinicians must rekindle their commitment to the time-honored traditions of associative and deductive reasoning. In doing so, they safeguard not only their patients' health but also the very sanctity and dignity of the medical profession.

Conflicts of interest

Dr. Diamandis heads the non-profit laboratory that developed Amitradicain, a composite drug formula for the relief of pathologically elevated sympathetic tone, the formula of which has been made non-commercially open source.

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References

1. Honda, R., Asgari, A., Simon, N., & Diamandis, C. (2023). Amitradicain - Managing Oshtoran Syndrome (Case Study II). In Zenodo ePub: Bde. 08/23 (17.6). Zenodo ePub. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10003560>
2. Atanackovic D, Dalgaard-Mikkelsen S: Procaine and autonomic innervation. *Proc Soc Exp Biol Med.* 1950 May;74(1):55-6. doi: 10.3181/00379727-74-17807. PMID: 15430388
3. Honda, R., Asgari, A., & Nathan, S. (2023). Amitradil - A safer alternative to Amitradicain for managing of Oshtoran Syndrome in patients with heart issues and all types of diabetes. In Zenodo ePub: Bde. 10/23. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10003956>
4. Cooper, I: Procaine injection of the globus pallidus in Parkinsonism. *Psychiatr Q.* 1954 Jan;28(1):22-3. doi: 10.1007/BF01567035. PMID: 1315568
5. Johansen J, Yang J, Kleinhaus AL. Actions of procaine on specific nociceptive cells in leech central nervous system. *J Neurosci.* 1984 May;4(5):1253-61. doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.04-05-01253.1984. PMID: 6726331; PMCID: PMC6564940
6. Koerts J, Leenders KL, Brouwer WH. Cognitive dysfunction in non-demented Parkinson's disease patients: controlled and automatic behavior. *Cortex.* 2009 Sep;45(8):922-9. doi: 10.1016/j.cortex.2009.02.014. Epub 2009 Mar 11. PMID: 19327762.
7. Redding VJ, Rees JR. Early changes in collateral flow following coronary artery ligation: the role of the sympathetic nervous system. *Cardiovasc Res.* 1968 Jul;2(3):219-25. doi: 10.1093/cvr/2.3.219. PMID: 4970325
8. Tudor, A., Asgari, A., Nathan, S., & Honda, R. (2023). The impact of branding on patient reception and therapeutic efficacy of composite pharmaceutical Amitradicain in Oshtoran Syndrome management. In Zenodo: Bde. 10/23. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1003053>
9. Unpublished data
10. Liu-Seifert H, Andersen S, Case M, Sparks J, Holdridge KC, Wessels AM, Hendrix S, Aisen P, Siemers E. Statistical properties of continuous composite scales and implications for drug development. *J Biopharm*

- Stat. 2017;27(6):1104-1114. doi: 10.1080/10543406.2017.1315819. Epub 2017 Apr 27. PMID: 28402165
11. D'Iorio A, Guida P, Maggi G, Redgrave P, Santangelo G, Obeso I. Neuropsychological spectrum in early PD: Insights from controlled and automatic behavioural regulation. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2021 Jul;126:465-480. doi: 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2021.04.003. Epub 2021 Apr 6. PMID: 33836213
12. Birnboim S. The automatic and controlled information-processing dissociation: is it still relevant? *Neuropsychol Rev.* 2003 Mar;13(1):19-31. doi: 10.1023/a:1022348506064. PMID: 12691499.
13. Singer, W., Mauermann, M. (2014). *Autonomic Neurology.* United Kingdom: Oxford University Press.
14. Robertson, A. S. (2019). *Disorders of the Autonomic Nervous System.* (n.p.): CRC Press.
15. Colombo, J., Arora, R., DePace, N. L., Vinik, A. I. (2014). *Clinical Autonomic Dysfunction: Measurement, Indications, Therapies, and Outcomes.* Germany: Springer International Publishing.
16. *Autonomic Dysfunction in Parkinson's Disease.* (2021). Netherlands: Elsevier Science.
17. *Bedside Approach to Autonomic Disorders: A Clinical Tutor.* (n.d.). Germany: Springer International Publishing.
18. Colombo, J., Arora, R., DePace, N. L., Ball, C. (2014). *Clinical Autonomic Dysfunction: Measurement, Indications, Therapies, and Outcomes.* United States: Springer International Publishing.